

ACTION OF NITROGEN TETROXIDE AND NITROGEN DIOXIDE ON ZINC CARBONATE (AND ZINC SULPHIDE)

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Action of nitrogen tetroxide and dioxide and their thermal dissociation products on zinc carbonate has been investigated and nitrogen tetroxide has been found to react almost immediately in contact with zinc carbonate.

Action of nitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on metallic zinc and zinc oxide has been investigated by Addison, Lewis and Thompson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2829), and on anhydrous sodium carbonate by Addison and Lewis (*ibid.*, 1952, 1319). Calcium carbonate, when treated with nitrogen tetroxide or dioxide, is supposed to give only calcium nitrate (Briner, Lugin and Monnier, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 64). No further work is reported in the literature.

The author, while studying the reactions of nitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on oxides and nitrite, found that nitrogen tetroxide reacted almost immediately on contact with zinc oxide in accordance with the observations made by Addison *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). Zinc sulphide, identical in structure with zinc oxide, was also found to react instantaneously with nitrogen tetroxide and dioxide mixture. Some of the products of reaction were analysed and found to contain zinc nitrate as one of the products of reaction, but the whole system was found to be complicated. The reaction with zinc carbonate, which did not seem to be much complicated, has been thoroughly investigated in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Zinc carbonate used was extrapure A. R. chemical and its purity was established before working. Nitrogen tetroxide was prepared after Oza, Oza and Thaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2457).

Liquid N₂O₄ system.—Pure nitrogen tetroxide was condensed and filled in reservoir R (Fig. 1). The compound to be treated with liquid N₂O₄ was weighed in a small tube, d (diameter about 3 mm.) as shown in Fig. 2a. This was then drawn out by heating so as to convert it into a form of the type as shown in Fig. 2b. Proper care was taken to see that no compound stuck on the wall of the glass tube. This was then sealed up at Z (Fig. 1). The tube (d) with the substances in this position was then surrounded with a bath containing a freezing mixture (common salt + ice) at -10° to -15°, and maintained there for about 15 minutes. X was then opened and liquid N₂O₄ was allowed to be distilled rapidly in the tube. A slight reaction took place on contact of N₂O₄ with the substance, turning the colour of N₂O₄ slightly green (due to the formation of N₂O₃), but the N₂O₃, thus formed, remained adsorbed on the substance because of the low temperature. More N₂O₄ was allowed to be collected over the substance till the

tube was about $2/3$ filled. The liquid N_2O_4 , collected over the substance, retained its characteristic yellow colour, thus showing that N_2O_3 , slightly formed, remained adsorbed on the substance only. In case the colour of N_2O_4 over the substance was found to turn green, the experiment was rejected. R was then cooled by a bath of ice and water; tap X was closed and the lower part of the tube was removed by sealing at its capillary end. The sealed tube was then brought to 20° to 25° , and within a few minutes the substance reacted and the yellowish viscous liquid appeared in the tube in place of the white solid powder. The colour of the liquid (N_2O_4) turned greenish blue.

FIG 1

FIG. 2a. FIG. 2b.

FIG. 3.

Interesting observation was met with when the experiment was carried out with zinc sulphide (0.123 g. taken in tube d). Liquid N_2O_4 was allowed to be poured on the substance in the same manner as mentioned above with zinc carbonate. But on bringing the substance at room temperature, the reaction was found to be vigorous, showing the appearance of boiling of N_2O_4 , which turned greenish-blue; the tube then burst out with explosive violence. The gases evolved after explosion smelt of sulphur dioxide or sulphur trioxide. The solid residue contained at least zinc nitrate and zinc sulphide among the products. The reaction could be controlled if much smaller amount of zinc sulphide were used.

The tubes 'd' containing viscous liquid and condensed gases were allowed to remain at constant temperatures (22° to 25°) for hours and days.

The action of nitrogen dioxide on zinc carbonate was studied by the same method and apparatus as used by Oza, Oza and Thaker (Fig. 1, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2457).

Products of Reaction.—The tube 'd' containing all the products of reaction, kept for hours, was now taken for analysis. This tube was carefully cleansed and weighed. It was then inserted in another tube α (Fig. 3) having a detachable ground-glass joint. The tube 'd' was placed in such a way that when α was fixed to A (as shown in Fig. 3), its capillary portion passed through the bore of the key of the tap, as shown in Fig. 3. This whole part A was then joined to the main system, as shown in Fig. 1 [Oza, Oza and Thaker, *loc. cit.*] by means of its ground-glass joint. The apparatus was evacuated, 'b' was closed, and dry air was introduced in the system; a strong potash lye was filled in C, D and E, and again the apparatus was evacuated. The capillary end of the tube 'd' was then broken and the gaseous products were cooled in P. 'b' was then opened and the nitrous fumes were allowed to be absorbed in alkali*. When the apparatus was clear of the nitrous fumes, dry air was introduced in the system by breaking the capillary end of α . 'd' was removed quickly and sealed. The broken pieces were also removed and collected, washed with dry ether and weighed along with 'd'. Solutions in alkali bulbs were mixed and made to a known volume and analysed for nitrite and nitrate; from these results the amounts of N_2O_3 and N_2O_4 in the gaseous mixture were calculated. It was difficult to analyse carbonate in presence of nitrite, but its analysis was not necessary. The tube 'd', now containing the viscous product only, was weighed and placed in α , as done before, and the system was evacuated. Alkali was then filled in C, D and E, taking necessary precautions. The tube 'd' was again broken at its capillary end. The tube was now surrounded by a heating contrivance and temperature was raised slowly to 100° . The heating was continued till the yellow viscous liquid changed to a white powder, and no more bubbles escaped in alkali bulbs. The tube 'd' along with its broken pieces was removed as usual and weighed. The residue was dissolved out in water. Almost a negligible amount of the substance was left insoluble. The water-soluble portion was analysed for nitrite and nitrate, and only nitrate was formed. The solution in the alkali bulb was analysed for nitrite and nitrate, and as usual calculations were made for N_2O_3 and N_2O_4 .

In the gaseous system zinc carbonate was allowed to react with nitrogen dioxide for one hour at different temperatures. The bath was maintained at the temperature of experiment till all the nitrous fumes from the system were absorbed in alkali. The residue at the end of the experiment was quickly weighed and dry carbon tetrachloride was added to the residue to remove the adsorbed nitrous fumes, and the carbon tetrachloride solution containing dissolved nitrous fumes was poured on alkali solution (about 1 N) and shaken vigorously. The aqueous portion was examined for nitrite and nitrate contents. The residue after treatment with carbon tetrachloride was dried and dissolved in water. The soluble portion was made to a known volume through filtration. The insoluble residue was analysed for unchanged zinc carbonate by determining its zinc content volumetrically by standard $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. Carbon dioxide was calculated from zinc carbonate used up.

* The notations used refer to Fig. 1 of Oza et al. (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Action of nitrogen tetroxide on zinc carbonate.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Expt. No.	Period of contact.	ZnCO ₃	N ₂ O ₄ found.	Wt. of V.P.	Decomp. of V.P.	Zn(NO ₃) ₂ ·N ₂ O ₄		N ₂ O ₄ consumed	N ₂ O ₃ formed.	CO ₂ calc.	Approx. ratio.		
											9:3, 7:6, 10:11.		
1	6 hours	0.0204 g. (1.627 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.3251 g. (35.33 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0627 g. (1.68 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0909 g. (1.63 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0298 g. 3.24 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.2637 g. (28.82 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0614 g. (6.66 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.01335 g. (1.73 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.00716 g. (1.62 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4	2	1
2	24 hours	0.035 (2.79 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.400 (43.5 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1000 (2.7 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.03364 (2.81 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0525 (5.695 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.2850 (30.9 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.115 (12.5 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.02087 (2.74 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0123 (2.79 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4.4	2.	1
3	7 days	0.0457 (3.644 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.3752 (40.77 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1401 (3.75 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0708 (3.68 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0657 (7.12 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.243 (26.2 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1322 (14.3 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.02666 (3.5 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.01603 (3.644 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4	2	1
4	1 month	0.0505 (4.04 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.389 (43.3 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1584 (4.24 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0772 (4.04 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0739 (8.04 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.2462 (26.7 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1428 (15.5 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0315 (4.14 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.1772 (4.02 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4	2	1
5	2 months	0.025 (1.992 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.396 (43.4 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0784 (2.1 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0386 (1.996 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0361 (3.87 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.3138 (34.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.0776 (8.4 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.01737 (2.24 × 10 ⁻⁴)	0.00877 (1.992 × 10 ⁻⁴)	4.4	2	1

* Gram molecular quantities are shown in parenthesis.

V.P. denotes viscous product.

TABLE II

Action of nitrogen dioxide on zinc carbonate

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Expt. No.	Temp	ZnCO ₃ taken.	N ₂ O ₄ taken.	Residue taken.	Residue found	Zn(NO ₃) ₂ , ZnCO ₃ .	ZnCO ₃ used up.	Adsorbed gases.	N ₂ O ₄ left.	N ₂ O ₄ used up.	N ₂ O ₃ formed.	CO ₂ (calc.)	Approx. ratio.		
1	2°	0.1000 g.	0.1904 g.	0.144 g.	0.07892 g.	0.050 g.	0.00797 g.	...	0.1084 g.	0.0741 g.	0.03054 g.	0.01718 g.	2	1	
					(4.17 × 10 ⁻⁴)		(3.97 × 10 ⁻⁴)			(8.03 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(4.03 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(3.978 × 10 ⁻⁴)	8:12. 13:14.		
2	10°	0.1034	0.2535	0.1795	0.1184	0.01681	0.0926	0.02136	0.001g.	0.0918 g.	0.1464	0.05375	0.0326	2	1
					(7.31 × 10 ⁻⁴)		(7.36 × 10 ⁻⁴)			(15.27 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(7.37 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(7.41 × 10 ⁻⁴)			
3	60°	0.100	0.161	0.142	0.0987	0.03546	0.06454	...	...	0.07665	0.09035	0.038	0.01852	2	1
					(5.21 × 10 ⁻⁴)		(5.14 × 10 ⁻⁴)			(9.82 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(5.15 × 10 ⁻⁴)			
4	80°	0.105	0.167	0.1401	0.09112	0.04705	0.05795	...	...	0.0828	0.0842	0.03563	0.02033	2	1
					(4.81 × 10 ⁻⁴)		(4.62 × 10 ⁻⁴)			(9.15 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(4.69 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(4.62 × 10 ⁻⁴)			
5	100°	0.1034	0.166	...	0.1010	0.0404	0.063	...	...	0.0682	0.0978	0.0382	0.02408	2	1
					(5.33 × 10 ⁻⁴)		(5.02 × 10 ⁻⁴)			(10.6 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(5.03 × 10 ⁻⁴)	(5.02 × 10 ⁻⁴)			

The gram molecular quantities are shown in parenthesis.

DISCUSSION

As seen from Table I, the quantities of nitrogen tetroxide and zinc carbonate used up are in the ratio of 4 : 1; the reaction with zinc carbonate in liquid system thus appears to proceed according to the equation,

That the reaction is running exactly in this manner is further supported by the formation of N_2O_2 and CO_2 in equimolecular quantities. Viscous product must be a compound having the formula, $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$, as has been proved from the results of its decomposition.

The ratio obtained in column (13) is in accordance with the above equation. The reaction in the gaseous system is found to proceed according to

followed by rapid absorption of NO_2 by zinc nitrate formed, so as to form the yellow viscous complex.

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